

Progressive Damage Analysis of 3D Woven Composites Based on Decoupled Multi-scale Method

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Introduction

□ 3D woven CFRP

- Three-dimensionally oriented fiber bundles
- Higher impact resistance than UD-CFRP laminates
⇒ Applied in aerospace industry

Challenges

- Prediction of damage behavior with consideration of complex structure
- Reduction of the number of component tests

Efficient numerical method for simulating damage propagation behavior of 3D woven CFRP components is demanded.

3D woven CFRP model

Introduction

□ Strength prediction using conventional homogenization method

- Assuming that microscopic structure is set up periodically
- Adopted only for uniform deformation in macroscopic scale

Microscopic scale

(RUC : Representative Unit Cell)

Macroscopic scale

(CFRP plate)

Objective

- Proposing simulation method of **progressive damage of 3D woven composites**
- Adopting proposed method to **macroscopic non-uniform deformation**

Multi-scale analysis

- **Two scale analyses** for woven structure

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \underline{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(\text{per})}$$

$$\underline{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}(x) = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y \boldsymbol{\sigma} dy$$

Microscopic variables
Macroscopic variables

□ Micro-macro coupled method : Conventional

- Both of two scale analyses must be carried out **alternately**.
- Microscopic analysis is carried out at **every integration points** of macroscopic model.

High calculation cost \Rightarrow Unrealistic for progressive damage simulation

Decoupled multi-scale method

- Identifying macroscopic constitutive law by microscopic analysis
⇒ **Non-simultaneous analyses**
- Lower calculation costs than previous method

Effective method for damage simulation of woven composites.

Decoupled multi-scale analysis

Microscopic analysis
(RUC of woven CFRP)

Macroscopic analysis
(U-shaped beam structure)

□ Microscopic scale

□ Macroscopic scale

- Woven structure
- Damages modeling
- Analysis
- Identifying constitutive law
- Analysis
- Validating the proposed method

Bamboo weave

□ Textile composites used in this study

Cross section of Bamboo woven CFRP (90deg layer)

- Fiber is oriented in one direction.
- Nylon binders are woven orthogonally.

■ Matrix ● Fiber — Binder

Schematic

Specimen

Microscopic damage modeling

Considering transverse crack and interface debonding as typical damages of woven structure

① Transverse crack

Modeled by continuum damage mechanics (CDM) model

□ Constitutive law

$$\sigma = C\varepsilon, C = f(d_2)$$

Expressing stiffness degradation by Transverse damage variable d_2

□ Damage evolution law

$d_2 = g(y_{d_2}) \Rightarrow$ Identified by experiment

$$e = \frac{1}{2} \sigma : \varepsilon$$

$$y_{d_2} = -\frac{\partial e}{\partial d_2} \Rightarrow \text{calculated by strain}$$

② Interface debonding

Modeled by cohesive zone model (CZM)

C : Stiffness tensor
 d_2 : Transverse damage variable
Undamaged $\rightarrow 0$
Completely damaged $\rightarrow 1$
 e : Helmholtz free energy per unit area
 y_{d_2} : Damage conjugate variable

Microscopic analysis model

Carried out by
Abaqus/Standard 2018

Nodes : 148,153, Elements : 242,392
 Fiber bundles : hexa element (C3D8), Resin : tetra element (C3D4)
 y_1 6.12 mm \times y_2 6.12 mm \times y_3 3.12 mm

Bamboo weave CFRP laminate $[0_3/90_3]_S$ is modeled. (Nylon binders are not considered)

□ Conditions

y_1, y_2 tensile, y_1y_2 shear
 y_1, y_2 bending, y_1y_2 torsion

- **Periodical boundary conditions** are given, using Key-DOF method.
- **Macroscopic unit strain and curvature** are forced.

Parameters of fiber bundle	
$E_L = 152.9\text{GPa}$	$E_T = 9.7\text{GPa}$
$\nu_{LT} = 0.373$	$\nu_{TT} = 0.450$
$G_{LT} = 4.5\text{GPa}$	
Parameters of resin	
$E = 3.1\text{GPa}$	$\nu = 0.438$

Microscopic analysis

y_1 tensile

Stress σ_{11} [MPa]

- Stress resultant N_{11} increases linearly and warp fiber bundles are under stress σ_{11} .
- N_{22} increases non-linearly due to transverse damage of weft fiber bundle.

Relationship between N_{11} and E_{11}^{macro}

Relationship between N_{22} and E_{11}^{macro}

Microscopic analysis

y_2 bending

Stress σ_{22} [MPa]

- Moment resultant M_{22} increases linearly and weft fiber bundle is under stress σ_{22} .
- M_{11} increases non-linearly due to transverse damage of warp fiber bundles.

Relationship between M_{11} and K_{22}^{macro}

Relationship between M_{22} and K_{22}^{macro}

Decoupled multi-scale analysis

Microscopic analysis
(RUC of woven CFRP)

Macroscopic analysis
(U-shaped beam structure)

□ Microscopic scale

□ Macroscopic scale

- Woven structure
- Damages modeling
- Analysis
- Identifying constitutive law
- Analysis
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Macroscopic constitutive law

□ Constitutive law

Relationship between stress resultant and unit strain

$$N = AE^{\text{macro}}, A = f(D)$$

U-shaped specimen

➤ Damage is modeled by CDM model.

- Warp fiber bundle direction at microscopic model $\Rightarrow D_1$
- Weft fiber bundle direction at microscopic model $\Rightarrow D_2$

□ Damage evolution law

$D = f(Y_D) \Rightarrow$ Identified by microscopic analysis

$$e = \frac{1}{2} N : E^{\text{macro}} + \frac{1}{2} M : K^{\text{macro}}$$

$Y_D = -\frac{\partial e}{\partial D} \Rightarrow$ Calculated by strain and curvature

A : In-plane stiffness matrix
 D : Macroscopic damage variables
 Undamaged $\rightarrow 0$
 Completely damaged $\rightarrow 1$
 e : Helmholtz free energy per unit area
 Y_D : Damage conjugate variables

Identifying constitutive law

- Damage variables D
 \Rightarrow Obtained from Stiffness degradation of microscopic analysis
- Damage conjugate variables Y_D
 \Rightarrow Calculated by macroscopic strain and curvature

Stiffness degradation of microscopic analysis

□ Damage evolution law

$$D = a_1[1 - \exp(-b_1 Y_{D1})] + a_2[1 - \exp(-b_2 Y_{D2})] + a_3[1 - \exp(-b_3 Y_{D1} Y_{D2})]$$

Fitting parameters

	D_1	D_2
a_1	0.05	0.40
b_1	0.151	0.133
a_2	0.40	0.20
b_2	1.501	0.156
a_3	0.0866	0.128
b_3	10381	4453.8

Relationship between D and Y_D

Macroscopic analysis can be carried out separately from microscopic analysis.

U-shaped flexural analysis

□ Analysis model

Nodes: 7701, Elements: 2500
Second order shell elements (S8R)

□ Conditions

- x_1 direction \Leftrightarrow Warp direction of microscopic model

Four-point bending analysis is carried out to investigate **the initial damage occurrence location and damage process.**

Four-point bending test

Investigating initial damage location

□ Results (Warp direction damage variable D_1 distribution)

- Damage occurs near to support and near to load point in analysis.
- Damage are observed near to support and near to load point in experiment.

Damage observation
(Left : outside, Right : inside)

Investigating initial damage location

□ Results (Weft direction damage variable D_2 distribution)

- Damage occurs near to support and near to load point in analysis.
- Damage are observed near to support and near to load point in experiment.

Proposed method can predict the initial damage location of U-shaped specimen.

Conclusion

Decoupled multi-scale damage analysis method for textile composite has been proposed.

- **Transverse crack and interface debonding** were modeled as typical damages of woven structure and macroscopic constitutive law was identified by microscopic analysis.
- **U-shaped beam structure** was chosen as macroscopic structure, and damage propagation was modeled by CDM model.
- **Four-point bending** analysis was carried out to investigate initial damage occurrence location and flexural test was also carried out for validating the proposed method.

The proposed method effectively simulated the initial damage occurrence location of macroscopic complex structure.